

Bibliometric Analysis of Bureaucratic Reform Articles in the Journal Scopus Written by Writers from Indonesia, Malaysia, And Singapore

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Abstract

This article discusses the bibliometric analysis of articles on bureaucratic reform in the Scopus journal written by authors from Indonesia, Malaysia, and Singapore. A search regarding bibliometric analysis of articles on bureaucratic reform in several databases such as Scopus, Google Scholar, Garuda (Garba Rujukan Digital), and Sinta (Science and Technology Index) has yet to be found. This analysis shows that the quantity of published articles from Indonesian authors is the highest compared to Malaysian and Singaporean authors. Then in quality, as seen from the number of citations, the articles of Indonesian authors still need to be improved to those of Malaysian and Singaporean authors. A study's keyword of bureaucratic reform can still be developed with other keywords from different scientific fields. The subsequent studies are expected to be able to understand other scientific works on bureaucratic reform more critically, not just articles, so that the knowledge of bibliometric analysis will continue to develop and become a novelty in the world of research.

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Introduction

The researchers around the world have conducted many literature reviews using bibliometric analysis. They were looking at the data in the Scopus database dated January 15, 2023, the result of keyword "bibliometric analysis" totals 22,009 documents that have been published. There are 2,427 scientific papers discussed bureaucratic reform in the Scopus database. Then, for almost 29 years, articles discussing bureaucratic reform and Scopus indexed from Indonesia, Malaysia, and Singapore experienced fluctuations. Over time, the emergence of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) campaign, which was followed by the emergence of the Industrial Revolution 4.0, then the Covid-19 pandemic prompted many writers from the three countries to publish on bureaucratic reform from 2015 to 2023. Unfortunately, it has yet to be found who conducted a bibliometric analysis of bureaucratic reform, both in Scopus and in Indonesia.

The author has tried searching with the keywords "bibliometric analysis" and "bureaucratic reform" in the Google Scholar, Garuda (Garba Rujukan Digital), and Sinta (Science and Technology Index) databases, as well as in the Scopus database, but none has been found yet. Besides, during college, the author has not found a bibliometric analysis concerning bureaucratic reform, only a few have researched the application of the concept of bureaucratic reform in several institutions or agencies, both regional and national.

This bureaucratic reform is part of the scope of public administration studies. Paradigm-wise, public administration has experienced various developments to date. From the classical paradigm that emerged and developed from 1855 or 1887 until 1980, followed by NPM (New Public Management) which emerged and developed in the 1980s to the mid-1990s, and now is in the era of Good Governance continuing NPM from the 1990s (Kurniawan, 2007). In the classical model paradigm, public administration tends to focus on a government that is always power-based and oriented so that not a few policy products are made only to strengthen state power over the people further (Razak, 2021). In fact, it is considered not focused on results but more focused on procedures and processes, insensitive to public needs, slow, red tape, and inter

alia (Kurniawan, 2007).

The development of thinking about public administration gave rise to a new paradigm which at that time was considered renewal with the emergence of the New Public Management (NPM). The essence of this paradigm is to run the government by managing companies (*run government like business*), which then encourages the emergence of a movement for bureaucratic entrepreneurship or Reinventing Government (Razak, 2021). According to Osborne's point of view, there are at least ten demands: decentralization, community-owned government, markets, entrepreneurship, customers, results, mission-oriented, competitive, anticipatory, and catalyst (Razak, 2021). Unfortunately, this paradigm is considered to reduce the values and essence of democratization, such as participation, representation, justice, and fairness (Kurniawan, 2007). Because market forces are often unable to fulfill the public's wishes, the public will only be considered consumers, so they will be far from having the right to participate as citizens (Drechsler, 2005).

Therefore, a new paradigm, namely Good Governance emerged as an improvement from the NPM. This paradigm was previously just Governance, which led to the development of a style of government with increasingly blurred boundaries between the private and public sectors (Stoker, 2004). This paradigm provides a large space for participation by building networks between the community and government to realize policy legitimacy (Stoker, 2004). Next, the Governance concept developed into Good Governance. The reason for adding the word "good" is to distinguish its implementation from "bad" (Kurniawan, 2007). More specifically, Good Governance is more focused on social and economic results by public expectations (Plumptre & Graham, 1999). It can be said that the change from one paradigm to a new paradigm shows the existence of bureaucratic reform that continues to adapt to the times.

According to Hegel, the bureaucracy is state administration or public administration, a neutral liaison between the government and society consisting of professional groups, entrepreneurs, and so on who

represent special interests (particular) (Daraba, 2019). Furthermore, when viewed from a governance perspective, *bureaucratic reform* can be defined as a major change in governance and governance paradigms. So that the professionalism of the government bureaucracy is realized with characters such as upholding the code of ethics and basic organizational values, free from corruption, collusion, and nepotism, integrity, and adaptability (Ministry of Transportation of the Republic of Indonesia, 2017). Then, another definition of *bureaucratic reform* is a step to rearrange the government administration system (aspects of management, institutions, and human resources), which are no longer efficient and effective, and are the core of the realization of good governance (Daraba, 2019; Prasajo & Kurniawan, 2008).

However, changes in the bureaucracy are considered the slowest component to change (Haning, 2018). Because the decentralized system is used to conduct corruption, collusion, and nepotism, there needs to be more in the quality of public services in various regions. There needs to be regulation of sanctions given due to poor service quality (Girindrawardana, 2002). In addition, bureaucratic reform can only succeed if it is influenced by several factors, such as bureaucratic culture, accountability, incentives, and power (Dwiyanto, 2002). The emergence of the industrial revolution 4.0 has also caused the bureaucracy to have the ability to collaborate, innovate, and utilize technology, information, and communication (ICT) (Amalia, 2018). Thus, it is not surprising that many papers discuss the use of concepts and theories from bureaucratic reform in state and regional institutions or institutions. So, this study will be a novelty.

In this study, the author will use the Scopus database as a provider of high-reputation education services at the international level which students and lecturers widely use in finding references when writing a scientific work. This study uses bibliometric analysis to construct and visualize articles on bureaucratic reform that are available in the Scopus database. The purpose of this study is to provide references and input for researchers, particularly Indonesian researchers, in studying a phenomenon of bureaucratic reform. This analysis also uses VOSviewer software to determine the most frequently cited references in specific

fields and identify potential research subjects (Utami, 2022). Furthermore, this study will also identify the evolution of publications from 1994 to 2023, a collaboration between authors, the use of keywords, and the direction of scientific concepts, which are then compared with data from Malaysia and Singapore to provide additional context.

Method

This study uses descriptive bibliometric analysis where the data source comes from the Scopus database from 1994 to 2023. Bibliometric analysis is a study that seeks to measure research progress obtained from literature such as documents, books, articles, journals and others which can be qualitative or quantitatively using statistical methods (Hakim, 2020). The data search began on January 15, 2023 with the keyword "bureaucratic reform", which was then limited to Indonesia, Malaysia, and Singapore and only to article document types. In the search option for a field of study in Scopus, the author chose the fields of "Social Science", "Business, Management and Accounting", "Economics, Econometrics and Finance", "Decision Science", "Environmental Science", and "Arts and Humanities".

As a result, the authors obtained 69 articles, stored in RIS files which were then used in the VOSviewer software to analyze the authors and the keywords used. When entering the RIS file, the author restricts keywords, not by the topic being studied.

Result and Discussion

a. Publication of Articles on Bureaucratic Reform by Indonesian, Malaysian and Singaporean Writers

In the Scopus database, Google Scholar, Garuda (Garba Rujukan Digital), and Sinta (Science and Technology Index) which discuss bibliometric analysis of articles on bureaucratic reform, have yet to be found. More specifically, there are no writers from Indonesia, Malaysia, and Singapore. Meanwhile, the publication of articles from the three countries from 1994 to 2023 has reached 69 articles. It can be seen in

Figure 1.

Figure 1: Articles Publications from 1994-2023

Source: (Scopus, 2023)

Figure 1 shows publications from 1994 to 2006 experienced stable ups and downs, although in 1998, there was a reasonably high increase. Then in 2002 to 2006 there was a publication vacuum. However, it experienced a significant increase until 2023 even though only one publication was recorded since the author carried out data collection. Most publications occurred in 2020 with a total of eleven published articles.

The reappearance of publications after the vacancy phase in the range of 2002 to 2006 can be said to be due to the emergence of the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) campaign (which we now know as the Sustainable Development Goals) which experienced delays in implementation in Southeast Asian countries, so that they could only be implemented several years after it was declared (Panuluh & Riskia, 2015). This also impacted the research and publications conducted on the use of the concept of bureaucratic reform, which immediately increased in 2007. Then in 2010 and after, publications continued to occur even though they fluctuated. The consistency of these publications likely due to the emergence of the Industrial Revolution 4.0, the SDGs, and the Covid-19 pandemic. The year 2010 experienced an increase due to the

start of the Industrial Revolution 4.0 (Sari & Priatna, 2020), 2015 was driven by the SDGs (Panuluh & Riskia, 2015), and the Covid-19 pandemic drove 2020.

In addition, the increase in publications since 2018 was also driven by requests for scientific publications for researchers, lecturers, and students in local to international journals to fulfill graduation and promotion requirements (Putera, Suryanto, Ningrum, 2020). In more detail, the author presents the publication of articles per year from each country in the figure below.

Figure 2: Indonesian Author Article Publications

Source: (Scopus, 2023)

Figure 3: Malaysian Author Article Publications

Source: (Scopus, 2023)

Figure 4: Singapore Author Article Publications

Source: (Scopus, 2023)

Most publications were made by writers from Indonesia, with a total of 41 articles, followed by writers from Singapore with 22 articles, and writers from Malaysia with eight articles published. The increase in the publication of scientific papers, especially this article, was also driven by several incentive programs obtained from the budget allocations of several government agencies and institutions engaged in research as affiliates of the authors (Putera, Suryanto, Ningrum, 2020). Some of these affiliations as in the diagram below.

Diagram 1: Top 10 Affiliation

Source: (Scopus, 2023)

Diagram 1 shows that there are five affiliated institutions from Indonesia (Padjadjaran University, Gadjah Mada University, Semarang State University, Syiah Kuala University, and University of Indonesia), followed by 4 institutions from Singapore (Singapore Management University, Lee Kuan Yew School of Public Policy, Nanyang Technological University, and National University of Singapore), and only 1 institution from Malaysia (Universiti Sains Malaysia). The data above shows that in terms of publications in terms of affiliation, Singapore still has the most publications with a total of 26 publications, followed by Indonesian affiliates with a total of 14 publications, and Malaysian affiliates with three articles. However, the highest number of publications is still held by Indonesian authors, as shown in figure 2. Of course, this cannot be separated from the journal where the article was published and indexed by Scopus, as shown in the table below.

Table 1: List of Scopus Indexed Journals Authors from Indonesia, Malaysia and Singapore from 1994 to 2023

No	Indonesia		Malaysia		Singapore	
	Journal	Number of Articles	Journal	Number of Articles	Journal	Number of Articles
1	Academy of Strategic Management Journal (Q3)	3	Academy of Strategic Management Journal (Q3)	1	International Journal of Public Administration (Q2)	4
2	International Journal of Innovation, Creativity and Change (Q2)	3	Global Business Review (Q2)	1	Asia Pacific Business Review (Q2)	1
3	Quality – Access to Success (Q4)	3	International Journal of Public Administration (Q2)	1	Asian Journal of Political Science (Q3)	1
4	International Journal of Supply Chain Management (Q3)	2	International Social Work (Q1)	1	Asian Politics and Policy (Q3)	1
5	Journal of Indonesian Legal Studies (Sinta 1)	2	Journal of Asian Economics (Q2)	1	China Economic Review (Q1)	1

Source: (Scopus, 2023)

Table 1 shows the journals used by authors from each country to publish their articles. Indonesian writers are dominant in publishing their articles in journals with a Q3 index. There is a unique thing in that one of the journals used by writers in Indonesia is not listed in Schimago Jr. However, it is listed in the Sinta index

(Science and Technology Index), which is a scientific publication database belonging to the Ministry of Education, Culture, Research and Technology of the Republic of Indonesia. The strength of Sinta 1 is included in the influential category and has become a reference for researchers, lecturers, and students in compiling scientific work. Sinta is connected to Scopus, so the credibility and quality are excellent. Then, writers from Malaysia and Singapore tend to publish their articles in all Scopus quartile indexes. Although in terms of index, Malaysian and Singaporean writers are still above Indonesian writers, in terms of quantity, Indonesian writers are still far more numerous.

b. Development of Article Publication on Bureaucratic Reform Authors (Co-Authorship) for Indonesia, Malaysia and Singapore

Writers dominated the publication of articles on bureaucratic reform from Indonesia with 41 articles. However, if you look at the names of the authors and the total of publications, it can be seen in the image below.

Figure 5: Top 10 Authors of Articles on Bureaucratic Reform Indonesian, Malaysian and Singaporean Writers

Source: (Scopus, 2023)

It can be seen that the dominance of writers from Indonesia in Figure 5 (such as Darsono, Rodiyah, Adam, Ahmad, Akbar. R, Akbar. Z, and Alam. S). While for Singapore, there is only Chen. K only. The rest, Tsang

came from the United States, and Turner came from Australia. No authors from Malaysia are included in the list of authors in figure 5. Writers such as Tsang and Turner could enter the list above because of their affiliations with institutions from Singapore and Indonesia. This happens because a collaboration exists between the author and related institutions in conducting research. It can be seen in the author's visualization in the image below.

Figure 6: Overlay Visualization of Indonesian, Malaysian, and Singaporean Co-Authorship

Source: (VOSviewer, 2023)

Figure 6 shows a visualization of the network of writers from the three countries, which means no form of a network (edge) or circle (node) that connects writers. So, writers from these three countries, or even writers from foreign countries affiliated with one of the institutions in the three countries, have no collaboration. These results do not form clusters (edges and nodes) of writers from Indonesia, Malaysia, and Singapore. In the following, the author presents a list of foreign authors of bureaucratic reform articles published by Scopus from Indonesia, Malaysia, and Singapore.

Table 2: Foreign Countries Authors of Bureaucratic Reform Articles Published by Scopus from Indonesia, Malaysia, and Singapore

No	Indonesia		Malaysia		Singapore	
	Country	Number of Articles	Country	Number of Articles	Country	Number of Articles
1	Australia	5	Indonesia	3	United States	8
2	United Kingdom	4	United Kingdom	1	Thailand	3
3	Malaysia	2	Canada	1	China	2
4	Panama	1	Pakistan	1	South Korea	1
5	-	-	Australia	1	Japan	1

Source: (Scopus, 2023)

Table 2 shows the original authors from their respective countries who wrote articles and the involvement of foreign writers affiliated with each of the institutions in the three countries. Of course, the presence of these foreign authors will provide new experiences and knowledge for related countries affiliated with it. It will become a separate reference for academics, researchers, and research institutions in those countries in developing research on a phenomenon. However, the original authors from each of these countries also have good quality and reputations. It can be seen from how many articles are cited, as shown in the table below.

Table 3: Comparison of the Number of Articles Published on Bureaucratic Reform and the Number of Citations

No	Country	Number of Articles	Number of Citations	The Quality of Articles
1	Indonesia	41	187	4,56
2	Malaysia	8	144	18
3	Singapore	22	251	11,40

Source: (Scopus, 2023)

Table 3 shows that having the most publications does not always mean having the same quality. Indonesia does have a large number of publications than Malaysia and Singapore, even the sum of the publications from these two countries still cannot match the number of publications in Indonesia. However, in terms of

the number of citations, Indonesia is lower than Malaysia and Singapore. Therefore, it has an impact on the quality of the articles in which Malaysia has the best quality articles, followed by Singapore and Indonesia.

c. Roadmap for Publication Development Articles Bureaucratic Reform Writers of Indonesia, Malaysia and Singapore Based on Keywords (Co-Occurrence)

Figure 7: Co-Occurrence Network Visualization

Source: (VOSviewer, 2023)

Figure 7 shows the results of the co-occurrence mapping with VOSviewer software to provide an overview of the development of bureaucratic reform research, which can be divided into five clusters.

Cluster 1: red color consisting of the keywords local government, reform, Thailand, decentralization, India, and human.

Cluster 2: yellow color consisting of the keywords bureaucratic reform, public service, e-government, public organization, and culture.

Cluster 3: green color consisting of the keywords bureaucracy, politics, Southeast Asia, China, and developing country.

Cluster 4: blue color consisting of the keywords corruption, government effectiveness, legal reform, good governance, and good governance.

Cluster 5: purple color consisting of the keywords Indonesia, policy, bureaucracy reform, and higher education.

The five clusters above are grouped by color group and contain keywords used by writers from Indonesia, Malaysia, and Singapore in writing articles. Between one cluster and the other clusters, they are interconnected. As seen in Figure 7, the bureaucratic reform loop has a larger size, which shows that many articles discuss and use the keyword bureaucratic reform. However, these keywords can also be used or collaborated with other keywords with smaller loops in both one cluster and different clusters to get updates in the study of bureaucratic reform. The complete keywords used by authors from each country are shown in the table below.

Table 4: Comparison of Keywords in Bureaucratic Reform Article Publications from Indonesian, Malaysian and Singaporean Authors

No	Indonesia		Malaysia		Singapore	
	Keyword	Total	Keyword	Total	Keyword	Total
1	Bureaucratic Reform	12	Article	1	Bureaucracy	5
2	Indonesia	9	Catalysis	1	China	3
3	Public Service	5	Citizen Participation	1	Decentralization	3
4	E-Government	3	Empowerment	1	Corruption	2
5	Higher Education	3	Government	1	Government Effectiveness	2
6	Bureaucracy Reform	3	Human	1	Thailand	2
7	Local Government	2	India	1	Politics	2
8	Policy	2	Local Governance	1	Southeast Asia	2
9	Public Organization	2	Pakistan	1	Capacity Building	1
10	Culture	2	Political Social Work	1	Climate Change	1

Figure 9: Density Visualization Co-Occurrence

Source: (VOSviewer, 2023)

Figure 9 shows the density map of keywords processed through VOSviewer. If the frequency of using a keyword increases, the density, and the circle will become brighter. Meanwhile, if the frequency of using keywords is less, then the density and the circles will be dimmer. Figure 9 also shows a combination of keywords from the formation of keyword circles that intersect with each other and are even covered by other keyword circles. The keyword bureaucratic reform is more dominant in intersecting with the keywords public service and e-government. Thus, the keyword bureaucratic reform can still be combined with other keywords that do not intersect, such as developing country, corruption, politics, etc. The following author presents a general comparison of articles from each country.

Table 5: Comparison of Indonesian, Malaysian and Singaporean Articles

No	Country	Problem Mapping	Method	Theory	Result
1	Indonesia	The mapping of problems carried out by Indonesian writers was dominated by problems found in the country, both within the state and regional scope. As for discussing in a broader scope, namely ASEAN. Many issues often discussed include poverty related to public health, governance of both central and regional	Mostly use qualitative research methods	The theory is widely used in the west, especially in America and Europe.	The research results show an explanation of the causal relationship (causality) between the existence of discrepancies in the field and the expectations set forth in a program or policy, also explaining the changes that have occurred seen from a comparison of the past with the present. In addition, studies that

		government, administrative reform, implementation of programs and policies, quality of public services, accountability, employee performance, and implementation of e-government.			discuss organizations are more focused on the results of these organizations for learning (organizational learning) and the quality of performance of employees.
2	Malaysia	The issues raised are not only domestic but also from abroad, especially in Asian countries, and talk about organization, governance, global impact, and public services.	Mostly use qualitative research methods	The theory is widely used in the west, especially in America and Europe.	The research results explain a lot about the impact arising from the emergence of a phenomenon, the quality of the implementation of a policy or program, as well as the quality of the organization and employee performance.
3	Singapore	The problem mapping used by Singapore authors is complex, not only in the social field (such as state reform, organizational reform, effectiveness, policies, programs, and competencies) but also in several scientific fields (such as medicine, climate, and energy). In addition, as many as 40% of article reviews have been taken outside Singapore.	Mostly use qualitative research methods	The theory is widely used in the west, especially in America and Europe.	The results of the research provide many explanations regarding changes in the conditions of a country or an organization when a reform occurs. In addition, the discussion terms often used were policies, programs, and the impact of small and large changes, both positive and negative, that affect the performance of a government, institution, or organization.

Source: (Scopus, 2023)

Table 5 shows the general differences in Indonesian, Malaysian, and Singaporean articles. Indonesian articles focus more on domestic affairs, while Malaysian and Singaporean articles focus on outside their own country. This is in line with table 4, in which besides the locus, the fields of study are also quite aligned. Indonesian articles focus more on the social field, although only about one study is related to the health sector like Malaysian articles. Meanwhile, Singaporean articles are more complex with lots of links to science and technology. The articles from these three countries mostly use qualitative methods, and the theory is mostly from western countries, especially from Europe and the United States. The research results from the articles of the three countries almost have similarities because they have similarities in the context or concept discussed, namely related to bureaucratic reform.

Conclusion

Considering the previous results and discussions, this article provides an overview of the quality and quantity of articles on bureaucratic reform written by authors from Indonesia, Malaysia, and Singapore. In quantity, the number of articles published by Indonesian authors is the highest compared to Malaysian and Singaporean authors. However, the combined quantity of articles from Malaysian and Singaporean authors still needs to match the number of articles belonging to Indonesian authors. Then in terms of quality, as seen from the number of citations, the articles of Indonesian authors still lose to Malaysian and Singaporean authors even though they have less quantity. Of course, this is an opportunity for every researcher, academician, and research institution in each country to develop the scope of research studies to provide innovation from a scientific point of view. Indonesian, Malaysian, and Singaporean writers still have the same opportunity to continue to improve the quality and quantity of scientific paper publications, significantly articles. Comparing articles from these three countries shows that Indonesia is more focused on domestic issues than Malaysia and Singapore. In addition, the fields of study used by articles from Indonesia and Malaysia are more dominant in the social field. In contrast, articles from Singapore are more complex in the presence of scientific fields. The articles of the three countries have similarities in terms of method, theory, and research results. The keyword bureaucratic reform in a study can still be developed with other keywords from different scientific fields. Future studies are expected to critically understand other scientific works besides articles on bureaucratic reform. Therefore, the knowledge of bibliometric analysis will develop and become a novelty in the study.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors have disclosed no conflicts of interest.

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